

Sumber : Pujihartono.id

Kepada Yth:

Bpk/Ibu : Kepala Personalia

(isikan alamat perusahaan)

Dengan Hormat,

Berdasarkan informasi yang saya dapatkan dari papan pengumuman pada kantor post cabang semarang yang memberitahukan bahwa PT Sukses Maju sedang membutuhkan tenaga operator mesin bubut,dengan ini saya mengajukan laamaran pekerjaan untuk mengisi posisi tersebut.

Saya yang betanda tangan di bawah ini :

Nama : Albert Mangkubumi

Tempat / tgl. Lahir : Semarang,20 Januari 1980

Jenis Kelamin : Laki-laki

Pendidikan Terakhir : SMK Mesin Perkakas

Alamat : Jln Raden Fatah no 16 Semarang Jawa Tengah

No. Telepon : 0821 386 859 46

Sebagai bahan pertimbangan,berikut saya lampirkan :

1. Fotkopi Ijasah
2. Fotokopi SKHUN
3. Fotokopi SKCK
4. Fotokopi KTP
5. Fotokopi Transkrip Nilai

Besar harapan saya untuk bisa diterima dan bekerja pada perusahaan yang Bapak/Ibu pimpin.Terima kasih atas perhatiannya,dan saya ucapkan terima kasih.

Hormat saya,

Tanda tangan anda

(isikan nama anda)

<https://surat-lamaran-kerja-tulis-tangan-ku.netlify.app/>

https://dev.azure.com/surat-lamaran-kerja-tulis-tangan/_git/surat%20lamaran%20kerja%20tulis%20tangan

<https://dev.azure.com/surat-lamaran-kerja-tulis-tangan/surat%20lamaran%20kerja%20tulis%20tangan/wiki/wikis/surat-lamaran-kerja-tulis-tangan.wiki/1/Surat-Lamaran-Kerja-Tulis-Tangan-Baik-dan-Benar>

<https://social.microsoft.com/Profile/surat-lamaran-kerja-tulis-tangan>

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<https://www.twitch.tv/surat123123>

<https://www.twitch.tv/surat123123/about>

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<https://coub.com/surat-lamaran-kerja-tulis-tangan>

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<https://profiles.wordpress.org/jajal123/>

<https://bit.ly/3D8TcXf>

<https://bit.ly/3I44P5B>

<https://bit.ly/31aivez>

<https://bit.ly/3lkdc39>

<https://bit.ly/3I45aoT>

<https://bit.ly/3o2qKIC>

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<https://bit.ly/3D6uYwZ>

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<https://peatix.com/user/10221815/view> <https://speakerdeck.com/pujihartonoid> <https://www.wysp.ws/pujihartonoid/> <https://www.magcloud.com/user/pujihartonoid> <https://www.ted.com/profiles/31244866/about> <https://profile.hatena.ne.jp/pujihartonoid/> <https://stackapps.com/users/85080/pujihartonoid?tab=profile> <https://askubuntu.com/users/1508782/pujihartonoid?tab=profile> <https://stackoverflow.com/users/17283215/pujihartonoid?tab=profile> <https://www.authorstream.com/pujihartonoid/> <https://disqus.com/by/pujihartonoid/about/> https://flipboard.com/@pujihartonoid?from=share&utm_source=flipboard&utm_medium=curator_share <https://www.kongregate.com/accounts/pujihartonoid> <https://weheartit.com/pujihartonoid> <https://www.sbnation.com/users/pujihartonoid> <https://www.ninersnation.com/users/pujihartonoid> <https://www.revengeofthebirds.com/users/pujihartonoid> <https://www.turfshowtimes.com/users/pujihartonoid> <https://www.buffalorumblings.com/users/pujihartonoid> <https://myspace.com/pujihartonoid> <https://www.roleplaygateway.com/member/pujihartonoid/> <https://www.answers.com/u/pujihartonoid> <https://www.wattpad.com/user/pujihartonoid> <https://trello.com/pujihartonoid2> <https://github.com/pujihartonoid> <https://www.zippyshare.com/pujihartonoid7> <https://www.instructables.com/member/pujihartonoid/settings/?cb=1635590271> <https://www.buzzfeed.com/pujihartonoid> <https://dribbble.com/pujihartonoid/about> <https://www.kickstarter.com/profile/pujihartonoid/about> <https://visual.ly/users/pujihartonoid/portfolio> <https://www.goodreads.com/user/show/142291106-pujihartonoid> <https://about.me/pujihartonoid> <https://id.quora.com/profile/Pujihartonoid-Id-1> <https://www.discogs.com/user/pujihartonoid> <https://ask.fm/pujihartonoid> <https://serverfault.com/users/904461/pujihartonoid?tab=profile> <https://superuser.com/users/1606383/pujihartonoid?tab=profile> <https://webmasters.stackexchange.com/users/123993/pujihartonoid?tab=profile> <https://www.coursera.org/user/38ef6bbc6b4d94ea978302712969535e> <https://www.redbubble.com/people/pujihartonoid7/shop?asc=u> <https://www.producthunt.com/@pujihartonoid> <https://alternativeto.net/user/pujihartonoid/> <https://500px.com/p/pujihartonoid?view=photos> <https://pujihartonoid.livejournal.com/profile> <https://www.scoop.it/u/pujihartonoid> <https://webapps.stackexchange.com/users/285104/pujihartonoid?tab=profile> <https://meta.stackexchange.com/users/1092870/pujihartonoid?tab=profile> <https://diy.stackexchange.com/users/143263/pujihartonoid?tab=profile> <https://photo.stackexchange.com/users/102410/pujihartonoid?tab=profile> <https://knowyourmeme.com/users/pujihartonoid> <https://independent.academia.edu/idpujihartonoid> <https://myanimelist.net/profile/pujihartonoid> <https://www.ganggreennation.com/users/pujihartonoid> <https://www.patspul>

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